

TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION IN INNOVATIVE WAYS

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Annotation This article discusses about main characteristics of the innovative approach, features of its implementation in education and innovative teaching methods in the foreign language educational process. Using innovative ways to develop students' creative thinking in English lessons.

Key words: intercultural communication, innovative ways, social development, education, professional

The achievements of the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan over the years of independence have been widely recognized as a unique model for the accelerated formation of an independent state.

Against this background, a new understanding of the role of education took hold. It began to be considered among the fundamental factors and guarantees:

- ✓ national security and economic development;
- ✓ ensuring fundamental human rights and freedoms;
- ✓ social security, professional mobility, business career and high quality of life of the individual;
- ✓ establishment of law and order and the formation of civil society.

At the present stage, there is an intensive introduction of innovative technologies into the learning process. Modern requirements for domestic education are determined by the need to ensure accelerated socio-economic development in the training of professional personnel with managerial competence and adaptive and creative readiness to operate in conditions of knowledge-intensive high-tech production and innovative development of markets [2, 14].

Integration processes characteristic of modern times in the educational sphere inevitably put forward demands for the creation of unified internationally accepted programs for each stage of the continuous and successive education system with a correlated system of content, structures, standards and forms of certification.

Education becomes the main resource and mechanism for the reproduction of social intelligence. Its priority in all spheres of social life determines a new phase of our civilization - the formation of a society of the future as an educational community of a multipolar world.

Education reform began to be seen as a prerequisite and driving force for all vital areas of social development, with a leading focus on the economic modernization of the country. One of the priorities of the state educational policy is focusing on the use of world experience, which allows organizational and structural integration into the global education system, borrowing advanced technologies for managing the educational process, ensuring its flexibility, diversified variability and adaptability to the changing conditions and pace of socio-economic development of the country [2 , 14-16].

From a simple factor in social and state life, education becomes a genuine subject of transformation of society and gives rise to new forms of social life. Education acquires the status of a special mechanism for the social and cultural development of regions and the country as a whole, and becomes a space for the personal development of each person.

Education is the main capital that a person has in the labor market in a post-industrial and information society. Therefore, today, perhaps more than ever, it becomes the basis for personal development and a guarantee of social mobility and social sustainability of a graduate [1, 4].

By language education, linguodidacts define education in the field of all modern, native and non-native, languages and cultures [5, 118]. In developing a unified system of language education, the leading argument is the target objectives

of humanitarian education, provided mainly by subjects of the humanities cycle and aimed at the development and formation of an individual that meets the requirements of the modern multicultural and multilingual world, where the main functions of the language education system is the formation of an individual who speaks a non-native language. language as: a means of intercultural communication; a means of learning someone else's and one's national culture, one's own and other languages; a tool for free orientation and life in the modern multicultural and multilingual world; a holistic basis for orientation and selection of communicative behavior and non-verbal norms of interaction, taking into account the specifics of the development and state of countries, regions, and world civilization.

In the evolution of views on “education”, it is customary to highlight the classical theory, following the Western intellectual tradition, which defines education as the process of a person acquiring his image in space, culture [6, 36], according to which education is a way for a person to realize himself as a spiritual, rational , a free being through the ascent to everything, the ascent to culture, going beyond the limitations of one's own natural givenness [7, 57-63].

The modern concept of “education” is associated with the interpretation of such terms as “training”, “upbringing”, “education”, “development”. However, before the word “education” began to be associated with enlightenment, it had a broader meaning. Dictionary meanings consider the term “education” as a noun from the verb “to form” in the sense: to create, form or develop something new. Creating something new is innovation.

The current state of the theory and practice of teaching foreign languages, it should be noted that the strengthening of the social significance of foreign language education, along with positive processes, has brought to life a number of phenomena that are hindering the long-term development of foreign language education in the republic:

1. the unity of the educational space and the uniformity of the subject content of foreign language education were disrupted, as schools were overwhelmed with innovative experiments;
2. there was a lack of a unified methodological platform and theory of foreign language education, which affected the arbitrariness of the choice of options for educational programs and teaching aids;
3. the focus of training on standardized end results was lost due to the rapid development of the spontaneous market of foreign training programs and courses, textbooks and educational complexes, the choice of which was no less spontaneous and subjective;
4. due to the lack of a criterion mechanism assessing the levels of training of graduates of various types of schools working in various programs, it became impossible to determine the requirements for the quality of the final results;
5. as a result, the continuity and continuity of foreign language education was disrupted, which in this subject area is the main component that ensures the effectiveness and quality of education at all levels, including at the level of higher education.

The situation is aggravated by the insufficient level of personnel replacement and the low level of staffing of schools with foreign language teachers.

The time has come to analyze, comprehend and systematize the phenomena occurring in foreign language education, to determine starting positions and readiness to solve large-scale problems put forward by the demands of the time. Today, one thing is clear: modern requirements for the level of training in foreign languages dictate an active process of introducing a variable system of requirements into the theory and practice of teaching [3, 29-36].

Innovative educational projects are designed to implement the modern educational paradigm, the main content of which is individualization and personality-oriented education, increasing the possibility of creative self-realization

in the educational process, and the synergy of cooperation between teachers and students.

Innovation has always been characteristic of pedagogical activity as the most important characteristic reflecting the process of development of pedagogical science and practice. In modern education, innovations are becoming increasingly widespread. It is innovations today that are called upon to harmonize relations in the educational process, bring its results in line with the requirements of society and the individual needs of a person, and solve the problems of forming a socially useful and successful personality.

Innovation from the English innovation means innovation, novelty [16, 343]. The main indicator of innovation is the progressive beginning in the development of the school in comparison with established traditions and practices. Therefore, innovation in the education system is associated with making changes:

- goals, content, methods and technologies, forms of organization and management system;
- in the style of pedagogical activity and the organization of the educational and cognitive process;
- into the system of monitoring and assessing the level of education;
- into the financing system;
- in educational and methodological support;
- into the system of educational work;
- in the curriculum and training programs;
- in the activities of the teacher and the student.

Pedagogical and educational innovations represent a moment in the development of a pedagogical or educational system. In order for a pedagogical or educational innovation to be accepted by the system and become part of it, it must correspond to it. The sources of school renewal ideas are:

- the needs of the country, region, city, district as a social order;

- advanced pedagogical experience;
- intuition and creativity of managers and teachers;
- experimental work;
- Foreign experience.

Pedagogical science is an important source of pedagogical innovation. By changing ideas about the pedagogical process, about school, about quality standards about the learning individual, it serves as a generator of pedagogical innovations. Pedagogy, as its part, pedagogical innovation begins with human studies. After all, any pedagogical system, first of all, has the status of an anthropogenic system of the “person-person” or “person-society” type, in which knowledge about the laws of human development is manifested. The goals and objectives of innovation activity are:

- Improving teaching and education of students.
- Inclusion of teachers in activities to develop new content, new pedagogical technologies and new organizational forms of mass education.
- Dissemination of the best teaching experience.
- Involving scientists from research centers in educational problems.

Thus, pedagogical innovation is defined as an innovation, a purposeful change that introduces stable elements or innovations into the educational environment that improve the characteristics of individual parts, components and the educational system itself as a whole. Pedagogical innovations are born in the educational system as a moment of manifestation of the law of its wave readaptation to a changing external environment. Pedagogical innovation itself is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon. Pedagogical innovations cover pedagogical technologies or methods, the content of education, educational programs and standards, educational processes, organization of lessons, organization of the pedagogical environment of the school. The range of pedagogical innovations is

enormous. But in any case, pedagogical innovation must correspond to the “order”, “need” of the evolution of the pedagogical system, which brought it to life.

However, the educational material itself cannot yet provide students with creative thinking in the desired system, the implementation of which requires certain pedagogical conditions, namely:

- careful selection and optimal dosage of material for the lesson;
- personal significance of the subject content of the student’s activity;
- initial type of motivational structure;
- application of new technologies in teaching foreign languages;
- specifics of the academic subject and type of educational task.

The skillful use of techniques and methods that ensure high activity in educational cognition is a means of developing the creative abilities of students [10, 19-25].

Thus, for creativity there is no need to find additional time and, especially, special classes. Creativity should permeate the entire lesson, everything that is done in the lesson. Mandatory components of the lesson should be supplemented with creativity.

Creative thinking is defined as the process of receiving, processing semantically, preserving acquired knowledge and applying it in new situations, when solving practical and theoretical problems, that is, this knowledge is used in the form of a skill and, on its basis, new, original problems are solved [11, 357]

R.A. Fatkhutdinov notes that there are significant differences between the concepts of “novelty” and “innovation”. Innovation is a broader concept that can include not only the application of new knowledge in practice, but also discoveries, new forms of work organization, while innovation is the result of the introduction of innovation with the aim of changing the managed object. Innovations can be immediately introduced, becoming innovations, or they can be created, but do not find practical application in a given system, exist in the form of new ideas and projects, accumulate, “waiting in the wings before implementation” [4, 15].

So, according to our research, innovation is precisely a means, a new method, technique, technology, program, and innovation is the process of mastering this means. Innovation is a purposeful change that introduces new stable elements into the environment, causing a transition of the system from one state to another.

According to developed by A.V. Khutorskoy taxonomy divides pedagogical innovations into the following types and subtypes: [9, 17].

Innovative technologies today occupy a strong position in the life of the school, ensuring dynamic development, productivity and rapid adaptation of the educational process to changing conditions and demands of society.

In the educational process, real communication is necessary because it prepares for free communication. Therefore, it is so important to create situations of real communication in foreign language lessons, since their participants will be forced to communicate in a non-native language. It is this type of real communication that can be the beginning of work on the development of communicative competence.

As you know, speech exercises are based on the students' existing knowledge. Therefore, before explaining new material, speech exercises are offered to review previously studied topics.

Topic: Telephones and Computers.

Teacher: Telephones and Computers are very important things in our life. Do you agree?

Pupil: Yes, I do.

Teacher: Do you like telephones?

Pupil: Yes, I do. / No, I don't.

Teacher: Did you use your telephone yesterday?

Pupil: Yes, I did. / No, I didn't.

Teacher: Is it important to use technology?

Pupil: Yes, it is.

Teacher: When did you learn to use with a computer?

Pupil: I learned to work with the computer at the age of 15.

Teacher: What was your interest to computers in your childhood?

Pupil: My interest was playing computer games.

Teacher: Will your life become more interesting if you have a telephone?

Pupil: Yes, it will.

Shifting the emphasis from the teaching process to the learning process of the students themselves, their mastering the experience of self-education under the guidance of a teacher based on increasing independent work. This will allow students to develop an individually creative approach to mastering educational material, to the perception of sociocultural values, as well as carry out learning activities at their own pace and in accordance with their interests. Providing the educational process with material and technical means at the level of modern socio-cultural development of society.

In all cases, we consider innovative educational technologies as a link between science and practice, since it combines the characteristics of both and essentially reflects the relationship between them.

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